

CHEMICAL VAPOUR DEPOSITION OF TiC COATINGS ON SiC FIBRES FOR PROTECTION IN Ti-BASED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

TiC has been chosen as a prospective protective coating to prevent deleterious interfacial reactions between SiC fibre and Ti-alloy matrices. TiC coatings were chemically vapour deposited onto resistively heated SiC monofilaments from the chemical reaction between TiCl_4 and CH_4 , in the presence of excess H_2 at reduced pressure in a cold wall reactor. Deposition conditions, microstructure and chemical compositions of the TiC coatings were correlated to determine optimum deposition conditions for obtaining stoichiometric coatings with fine grain morphology and good adherence to the SiC fibres, which can be used as reinforcements in Ti-alloy matrices.

Keywords: CVD, TiC protective coating, SiC monofilament, Ti-based composites, deposition conditions, microstructure and chemical composition.

1. INTRODUCTION

TiC is an interstitial compound which has a melting point of 3250°C and a Vicker's hardness of 32 GPa, and is well known as a super-hard and refractory material [1]. These properties, together with its chemical inertness, have given rise to a wide range of applications as wear resistant coatings on cutting tools [2,3].

The thermal expansion coefficient of TiC is intermediate between SiC and Ti-alloy, and TiC has a high chemical stability (Gibbs free energy of formation, $G \ll 0$). Based on these physical and chemical compatibility consideration, TiC seems to be a promising protective coating for SiC monofilament to reduce and/or prevent the deleterious interfacial fibre-matrix reactions in Ti-alloy metal matrix composites (MMCs).

Chemical vapour deposition (CVD) technique has the ability to produce coatings of pure, dense, and of well controlled morphology and composition without relying on line-of sight between the source material and the substrate as required by other physical vapour deposition techniques. Moreover it offers the potential for continuous fibre processing. All these advantages make CVD the most common fibre coating technique.

The CVD of TiC in various forms (single crystals, polycrystalline layers [1,4] and whiskers [5] on graphite substrates [6]) has been widely studied. TiC has also been deposited on tungsten and carbon filaments [6-8]. However, publications on the deposition of TiC protective coatings on fibre substrates, especially ceramic fibres, are very limited. The nucleation and growth of TiC coatings on SiC monofilament fibres have not been clearly established. The technological difficulties encountered

in the fabrication of ceramic coated SiC monofilament by CVD have so far prevented these fibres from being studied widely.

Chemically vapour deposited TiC is most commonly fabricated by using TiCl_4 and a hydrocarbon or CCl_4 . This process has been widely used and proven as an economically and technically suitable method for the production of TiC coatings [9].

In order to obtain TiC coated SiC fibres that are suitable for use as reinforcement in Ti-alloy metal matrix composites, the coatings must have fine microstructure, stoichiometric composition and adhere well to the fibres. Therefore the study of the effects of deposition parameters (temperature, pressure and input gas ratio) on the nature of the coatings is essential to optimise the morphology, microstructure and composition of the coatings.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

TiC coatings were deposited on resistively heated BP Sigma SiC monofilaments (100 μm in diameter with a tungsten core) at reduced pressure in a cold wall reactor from the chemical reaction between TiCl_4 (Aldrich, 99.95% purity) and CH_4 (Aldrich, 99.0% purity) in the presence of excess H_2 (BOC, 99.99% purity) as follows:

The CVD apparatus used and the experimental procedures for the deposition of TiC onto the SiC monofilaments was essentially the same as described in reference [10]. The range of deposition conditions used are as follows:

substrate temperature	=	1000 - 1400°C
deposition pressure	=	8 - 25 kPa
$\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ gas ratio	=	2.5 : 1 - 1 : 3
H_2 flow rate	=	300 $\text{cm}^3\text{min}^{-1}$

These deposition parameters were systematically varied within the above ranges of interest to determine the optimum conditions for obtaining quality coatings. The substrate temperature was measured using a digital micropycrometer. The deposition chamber pressure was measured with an Edwards barocel pressure sensor. The flow rates of reactant gases were individually controlled by mass flowmeters.

The coating thickness, microstructure and adhesion were characterised using optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Deposition rate was calculated by dividing the average coating thickness over the deposition time. X-ray powder diffraction was employed for phase identification and determination of the crystallographic structure of the coating. A Cameca SEMPROBE (SU 30) equipped with a wavelength-dispersive spectrometer was used to study the composition of the coating using point microanalysis. The composition of the coating was determined from the average value of 10 points.

3. RESULTS

The CVD deposition rate and morphology of the TiC coatings were found to vary along the fibre due to the reactor geometry. Therefore all the coatings for analysis were taken from the same position, near the gas flow inlet which has a maximum deposition rate and gives a uniform coating morphology.

From the X-ray diffraction analysis, TiC was seen to be the dominant phase deposited under the conditions studied. Other phases such as Ti, Ti_2C and TiC_2 were not detected. This is in accordance

with the observation by Pearce et al. [11]. The appearance of the TiC coatings within the range of deposition conditions range studied was generally metallic grey.

The effects of deposition parameters on the morphology, microstructure and composition of the coating are described as follows:

3.1 Effects of Substrate Temperature

The deposition temperature has a large effect on the morphology of the deposited TiC coatings. Figure 1 shows that fine grains were deposited at lower temperatures as compared with coarser, faceted columnar crystals deposited at higher temperature. Intragranular cracks were easily observed in TiC coatings that were deposited at temperatures of 1200°C and above (example as shown in Figure 1c). These coatings also prone to delamination from the SiC fibre substrates, for example in Figure 2. The fracture surface of these coatings showed a typical transition from small grains near the substrate to columnar structure away from the substrate, Figure 3. Such crack pattern and microstructure transition were not observed in thin coatings deposited at 1150°C or lower. These TiC coatings deposited at low temperatures also showed better adhesion to SiC fibres (Figure 4). The deposition rate increases as the temperature increases (Table 1). From Table 2, it can be seen that the atomic ratio, x , in TiC_x increases with the increase in substrate temperature.

Table 1 Effects of substrate temperature on deposition rate. Other parameters were maintained at pressure 15 kPa, flow rates (cm^3min^{-1}): $TiCl_4$, 30; CH_4 , 75; and H_2 , 300.

Substrate Temperature (°C)	Deposition rate ($\mu m min^{-1}$)
1000	0.37
1150	2.05
1250	6.05

Table 2 Effect of substrate temperature on the atomic ratio, x in TiC_x .

Substrate temperature/°C	Atomic percentage		Atomic ratio, x in TiC_x
	Ti	C	
1000	48.54	51.46	1.06
1250	47.62	52.38	1.10
1400	46.73	53.27	1.14

3.2 Effects of CH_4 : $TiCl_4$ Gas Input Ratio

Table 3 and 4 show that as the concentration of CH_4 increases, both deposition rate and carbon content in TiC coating increase, while the grain size decrease (Figure 5). An equal input ratio of CH_4 to $TiCl_4$ produces larger crystals with a more stoichiometric TiC coating. Variation in reactant gas ratio has no significant influence on the fracture and adhesion characteristics of the coatings. All the TiC coatings that were deposited under varying CH_4 : $TiCl_4$ input gas ratio, but at the same deposition temperature and pressure, exhibited similar fibre fracture ends to that shown in Figure 4, and their coatings were not so easily spalled off.

Table 3 Effect of CH₄ : TiCl₄ gas input ratio on deposition rate. Other parameters were maintained at temperature 1000°C, pressure 15 kPa and H₂ flow rate 300 cm³min⁻¹.

Flow rate (cm ³ min ⁻¹)		CH ₄ : TiCl ₄ Gas Ratio	Deposition rate (µm min ⁻¹)
CH ₄	TiCl ₄		
75	30	2.5 : 1	0.37
30	30	1 : 1	0.26
30	90	1 : 3	0.12

Table 4 Effect of the CH₄ : TiCl₄ input gas ratio on the atomic ratio, x in TiC_x.

CH ₄ : TiCl ₄ gas ratio	Atomic Percentage		Atomic ratio, x in TiC _x
	Ti	C	
2.5 : 1	48.54	51.46	1.06
1 : 1	50.51	49.49	0.98
1 : 3	52.36	47.64	0.91

3.3 Effects of Deposition Pressure

The effects of pressure on the morphology of the TiC coating are shown in Figure 6. As the pressure increases, finer and less faceted grains were deposited. The increase in pressure caused the deposition rate to increase slightly (Table 5). Variation in pressure does not seem to have any significant influence on the stoichiometric of the coatings and the cracking mode of the coatings within the range investigated. All of the coatings exhibit a similar fibre fracture end to that shown in Figure 4.

Table 5 Effect of deposition pressure on deposition rate. Other parameters were maintained at temperature 1000°C, flow rates (cm³min⁻¹) : TiCl₄, 30 ; CH₄, 75 ; and H₂, 300.

Pressure (kPa)	Deposition rate (µm min ⁻¹)
8	0.28
15	0.37
25	0.45

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Microstructure

All of the TiC coatings have a typical faceted columnar microstructure, with very obvious "peaks and valleys" which may be favourable sites for crack initiation. These grain growth features, with rough and coarse surface morphology, are even more pronounced in coatings that were deposited at high temperatures. As the substrate temperature increases, the surface mobility of the absorbed atomic species becomes greater, leading to a higher rate of grain growth. However, this large grain morphology is not favourable for application as protective coatings in MMCs.

Increase in pressure seems to produce finer and less faceted grains. This may be because of increase in pressure from 8 kPa to 25 kPa, increases the supersaturation of the reactants and hence the nucleation rate. This may be due to the fact that an increase in the nucleation rate, leads to the formation of many nuclei at the surface of the substrate, which have insufficient time to grow into larger grains. As a result, finer and more rounded grains were deposited.

As the input gas ratio of CH₄ : TiCl₄ increases from 1 : 1 to 2.5 : 1, the deposition rate increases and the deposited TiC grains become finer. This may be due to the fact that with the increase in the concentration of methane (higher supersaturation), the nucleation rate is increased. However, a fine

grain morphology can still be found in the coating deposited at low input gas ratio of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ (i. e. high concentration of TiCl_4), for example as shown in Figure 5c. This may be due to the grain growth is retarded at high concentration of TiCl_4 . This effect is more pronounced when the TiCl_4 is very much in excess ($\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4 = 1 : 10$), the grain growth is retarded, and the coating became very brittle and exhibits cracking, Figure 7. This may be because of the fact that the substrate and coating were attacked by the corrosive TiCl_4 and HCl .

4.2 Chemical Composition

The stoichiometry of the TiC coating seems to vary with temperature. The amount of excess carbon seems to be increased at even higher deposition temperatures. This may be due to the fact that a higher deposition temperature enhances the pyrolysis of methane.

Although the increase in $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ ratio increases the tendency to deposit finer grains, the coating obtained containing an excess of carbon. The presence of an excess of carbon is undesirable because $\text{Ti}_2\text{SiC}_{1.25}$ can form if TiC becomes slightly substoichiometric in C [12]. However, coatings that were deposited at a gas input ratio of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ below 1 : 1 were deficient in carbon. As the $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ ratio increases from 1 : 3 to 1 : 1, TiC becomes more stoichiometric.

In short, the TiC coating has a considerable tendency towards substoichiometry. Therefore in addition to the deposition temperature, the control of the $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ gas input ratio is vital for the control of the stoichiometry of the TiC coating.

4.3 Coating Quality (Cracks & Adhesion)

Delamination and intragranular cracks in the coatings were easily observed in coatings that were deposited at high temperatures (1200°C and above). This may be due to the thermal shock developed during cooling as a result of a large mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) between TiC [CTE = $(7.6 - 8.9) \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ [12,13]] and SiC [CTE = $5.1 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ [12]]. Variation in $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ input gas ratio (1 : 3 - 2.5 : 1) and pressure (8 - 25 kPa) does not seem to have any significant influence on the cracking of the coatings.

Crack-free TiC coatings with better adhesion to the SiC fibres can be deposited successfully at low temperatures (<1150°C).

4.4 TiC as a Protective Coating

The incorporation of the stoichiometric TiC coated SiC monofilament fibres into Ti-6Al-4V matrix using the diffusion bonding technique (at 1100°C, 10 MPa for 1 hour) shown that the TiC coating has successfully retard the deleterious interfacial reaction between the uncoated SiC fibres and Ti-6Al-4V (which usually begin to occur at temperature above 700°C). Therefore TiC is a prospective protective coating for SiC fibres. A more detailed evaluation of the efficiency of TiC as protective coating for SiC fibres in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix will be described in reference [14].

5. SUMMARY

It was found that the deposition temperature, pressure and input gas ratio of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ can influence the morphology, microstructure and composition of the TiC coatings. TiC coatings deposited at lower deposition temperature (< 1150°C) tend to adhere better to the SiC fibres and give less cracking. However, variation in $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ input gas ratio and pressure have no apparent influence on the cracking of the coatings. Coatings with finer grains can be deposited at a lower deposition temperature (1000°C) and higher pressure (25 kPa). Deposition of TiC has a tendency towards substoichiometry, where the atomic ratio, x, in TiC_x increases with both increasing in substrate temperature and $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ input gas ratio. Therefore the control of the $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4$ input gas ratio and deposition temperature is critical for the production of stoichiometric coatings. The most stoichiometric TiC coating was obtained at a gas input ratio of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{TiCl}_4 = 1 : 1$ and a deposition temperature of 1000°C. The chemically vapour deposited TiC coating has successfully retarded the

deleterious SiC fibre-Ti-alloy matrix interfacial reaction in metal matrix composites. Therefore it is a promising protective coating for SiC fibre in Ti-based composites.

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Figure 1: SEM of the surface morphology of the TiC coatings deposited at various temperatures: a) 1000°C; b) 1150°C and c) 1250°C. All micrographs have the same magnification.

Figure 2: SEM of the TiC deposited at 1300°C shows delamination from the SiC fibre substrate.

Figure 3: Typical fracture surface of TiC coatings deposited at high temperatures (>1200°C), which shows the microstructure transition from fine grains near the substrate to a columnar structure away from the substrate.

Figure 4: SEM of the TiC coating deposited at 1000°C which shows good adhesion to the substrate.

Figure 5: SEM of the surface morphology of the TiC coatings deposited at different CH_4 : TiCl_4 input gas ratio: a) 2.5 : 1; b) 1 : 1 and c) 1 : 3. All micrographs have the same magnification.

Figure 6: SEM of the surface morphology of the TiC coatings deposited at different pressure: a) 8 kPa; b) 15 kPa and 25 kPa. All micrographs have the same magnification.

Figure 7: SEM of the TiC coating deposited under high concentration of TiCl_4 (CH_4 : TiCl_4 input gas ratio = 1 : 10)